

Some aspects of the coordination chemistry of cobalt(III)[†]

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Octahedral cobalt(III) complexes have played a central role in the elucidation of mechanisms of inorganic reactions. Some aspects of ligand substitution and redox reactions of low-spin octahedral cobalt(III) complexes in solution are discussed. The reactions include : (i) acid and base hydrolysis of halogenoaminocobalt(III) complexes, (ii) anation of aqua-aminocobalt(III) ions, (iii) acid, base and metal ion catalysed hydrolysis of carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes, and (iv) oxidation of ligands coordinated to cobalt(III). The halogenoaminocobalt(III) complexes derived from weakly basic amines have proved to be useful models for the elucidation of SN₁CB mechanism. The metal ion catalysed hydrolysis of carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes derived from dicarboxylic and phenolic acids have demonstrated the kinetic and thermodynamic implications of binuclear complexes of several substitution labile metal ions. Such entities are also models for the innersphere electron transfer reactions. Extensive studies of the ligand substitution reaction of a wide variety of cobalt(III) complexes have shown that the Co^{III}-X bond breaking generally takes precedence over the bond making between the incoming ligand and the cobalt(III) centre in the transition state. However, the ligand envelope of this metal ion mediates the reactivities of the complexes and further dictates the Co^{III}-X bond cleavage in the limits of interchange dissociative and/or fully dissociative modes.

The coordination chemistry of cobalt is in fact 4×10^9 years old¹. In that context one of Nature's famous system is Co corrinoids (vit. B₁₂ derivatives). It is Nature's high-tech material prevalent in biological domain. Although cobalt is a relatively rare metal in the earth crust, cobalt corrinoids appear to have been functionally important even before DNA. This has something to do with the thermodynamic and kinetic features of the corrinoids which occur as air-stable six-coordinate cobalt(III), five-coordinate cobalt(II) and reactive square-planar cobalt(I) species. It is, therefore, appropriate to say that cobalt has played a central role in the process of evolution.

The preparative work of Jorgensen, Werner and many others during the turn of the century opened up new vistas in coordination chemistry of transition metals. Werner's coordination theory did make it possible to understand at least the gross structural features of coordination compounds. Subsequent advances were made from various laboratories (of the West and East) with regard to the study of complex equilibria in solution, water being the common solvent. The theories of bonding helped to simplify the picture and provided great insight in understanding most chemical phenomena.

In referring to cobalt alone, it is rather amazing to find that this metal can form a wide variety of compounds in various oxidation states, ranging from 0 to +3 (or +4). However, studies are extensive for +2 and +3 oxidation states, the reason being that +2 state is stable under ambient conditions while +3 state can be stabilised to a great extent in

coordination complexes due to ligand field effect. While octahedral coordination is generally valid for Co^{III}, coordination numbers 4 and 6 are common for Co^{II}. The kinetic features of Co^{II} and Co^{III} complexes are very striking. The high substitutional lability of Co^{II} was perhaps an impediment for extensive study of coordination chemistry in +2 state till fast reaction techniques came into being. However, the kinetic inertness of Co^{III} complexes was advantageous for synthesis of a large number of such complexes and therefore, octahedral cobalt(III) complexes played a central role as models for understanding inorganic reaction mechanisms.

Substitution reactions

It will not be out of place to mention here the classic study of Bronsted and Livingstone² in 1927 on the kinetics of reactions of (NH₃)₅CoBr²⁺ with OH⁻ and Hg²⁺. However, this work was not aimed at probing the reaction mechanism, but served as a test of the theories of ionic strength effects on the rates of reactions. Garrick's suggestion³ in 1937 that OH⁻ can labilise an amine complex, (NH₃)₅CoBr²⁺, by NH-deprotonation, was in some ways epoch-making. Subsequently, Basolo and Pearson⁴ expanded this idea to develop the concept of the conjugate base mechanism for the base hydrolysis of cobalt(III) complexes. Indeed the generalised conjugate base mechanism of aqua and amine complexes owes its origin to the idea of Garrick³.

Taube's⁵ classification of labile and inert complexes was a systematic attempt to probe substitution reactions. The ligand field theory provided a basis for understanding the

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reactivities of transition metal complexes. The correlation between electronic structure and rates of substitution in terms of ligand field theory was proposed and developed by Basolo and Pearson^{4,6}.

The American school headed by Basolo and Pearson of North Western University gave a great thrust to the study of the mechanism of substitution reactions of transition metal complexes. The University College, London, was equally active in this area with a dedicated band of workers led by Ingold, Nyholm and Tobe. The controversy between the two schools of thoughts in regard to the role of OH⁻ in the ligand substitution reactions of cobalt(III) amine complexes was, in fact, exciting. While Ingold *et al*⁷ tried to establish their viewpoint of OH⁻ being an entering ligand, Basolo *et al* advocated the view of Garrick. This controversy led to considerable expansion of our understanding of the mechanism of base hydrolysis of cobalt(III) complexes with innovative research. With this brief introduction, I shall now dwell upon certain aspects of octahedral substitution at the cobalt(III) centre, which we at the Chemistry Department, Utkal University, Bhubaneswar, have strived to pursue during the last three decade. As such, this does not constitute a comprehensive review of the concerned area of cobalt(III) chemistry.

Co(OH₂)₅³⁺ ion :

This aqua-cation is often omitted from kinetic investigations due to its redox instability and high lability. A report by McAuley *et al*⁸ on the Cl⁻ substitution kinetics delineates this aspect :

$k_1 = 2.5 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($E = 26 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$); $k_2 = 200 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($E = 12 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) (at 8°).

The progressive replacement of the aqua ligands by NH₃ or amines decreases redox instability and the substitutional lability of the corresponding aqua complexes. In fact the aquapentamminecobalt(III), (NH₃)₅CoOH₂³⁺, is inert to intramolecular reduction and it undergoes substitution of the coordinated aqua ligand at least 6 orders of magnitude slower than Co(OH₂)₆³⁺ under ambient conditions. Noteworthy is the fact that the substitution lability of the aqua ligand depends very much upon the ligand envelope of cobalt(III).

Leaving group effects :

The acidopentaamminecobalt(III) ions, (NH₃)₅CoX²⁺, have been used to elucidate the effects of leaving group Xⁿ⁻

on the substitution kinetics. Langford⁹ suggested that the transition state for the aquation of such complexes (or the anation of (NH₃)₅CoOH₂³⁺ by Xⁿ⁻), reached highly endothermically, should exhibit at the most a weak bonding interaction between the cobalt(III) centre and the leaving group. This has been demonstrated in the rate-equilibrium relation, i.e. log k_{aquation} versus log $K_{\text{equilibrium}}$ plot is linear with slope = 1.0.

This aspect was further amplified by Haim¹⁰ who used the value of the formal equilibrium constant for the transition state of the aquation/anation process of the acidopentaamminecobalt(III) substrates,

Haim's calculation shows that Q^* depends virtually on the coulomb interaction indicating ion-pair like transition state.

Steric effects :

Steric crowding enhances the rate of ligand dissociation from the cobalt(III) centre. One classic example is the differential reactivities of *meso*- and (*d,l*)(dicloro)(butylenediamine)cobalt(III) in the aquation process. The *meso*-form in which the two methyl groups are on the same side of the chelate ring aquates 30 times faster than the *d*/racemic form¹². Steric acceleration in the rate of aquation of (RNH₂)₅CoCl²⁺ (R = alkyl group)^{13,14} with increasing bulkiness of R has been reported. However, the rate of aquation of chloropentamminecobalt(III) ion, N₅CoCl²⁺, slows down on changing the 5N donors from 5ammonia to bis(ethylenediamine)(ammonia), (triethylenetetramine)-(ammonia) and tetraethylenepentamine¹². A comparison is made for the aquation of a selective cobalt(III) complexes in Table 1. Decreasing the number of N-H groups in the amine ligand by *N*-alkylation also slows down the aquation rates of the halogenoamminecobalt(III) complexes¹². These observations strongly favour dissociative interchange mechanism (*I_d*) involving some degree of solute-solvent interaction through H₂O...HN hydrogen bonding. An uncertainty remains regarding the separation of the polar and steric influences of the amine ligands on the aquation rates of such complexes. The two effects may not be mutually exclusive. However, the electronic effects do not appear to be large for the saturated amine ligands. This is evident in the aquation of substituted pyridine and aniline complexes, *cis*-(en)₂Co(B)X²⁺ (B = substituted pyridine or aniline; X = Cl⁻,

Table 1. Rate and activation parameters for aquation of $cis\text{-}L_4\text{ACoCl}^{2+}$

Temp = 50.0°, I = 0.3 M						
L_4	A	Isomer	$10^5 k_{ac}/s^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger cal $\text{K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	
trien	NH ₃	β_2	1.8	22.2	-12	
	NH ₃	α	0.95	23.8	-8	
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	α	0.5	25.3	-5	
	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂	β_2	3.4	36.0	+3.0	
	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂	α	0.6	33.0	+19	
	C ₆ H ₅ N	β_2	0.8	34.9	+26	
	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ NH ₂	α	1.4	21.0	-18	
	imidazole	β_2	4.9	25.3	-0.2	
	imidazole	α	0.93	24.6	-5.7	
	bezimidazole	β_2	3.4	24.9	-2.6	
(en) ₂	NH ₃		0.04	23.9	-10	
	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ NH ₂		0.031	25.3	-20	
	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂		0.036	31.8	+17	
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂		0.014	26.7	-2.1	
	C ₆ H ₅ N		0.062	23.9	-5.4	

Br⁻)^{15,16}. A comparative listing of the rate and activation parameters for the spontaneous and acid catalysed aquation of carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes (Table 2) delineates the importance of steric and electronic effects of the carboxylato ligand (i.e. the leaving group) on the substitution reaction.

Table 2. Rate and activation parameters for aquation of $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CoO}_2\text{CX}^{n+}$

O_2CX	k_1^a s^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger cal $\text{K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	k_2^a $s^{-1} M^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger cal $\text{K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
(CH ₃) ₃ C	5.2			25.0		
(CH ₃) ₂ CH	2.6					
CH ₃ CH ₂	3.1					
CH ₃	8.0	25	-8	93	25	+2
ClCH ₂	5.8	26.3	-2			
Cl ₂ CH	16	26.4	-3.5			
Cl ₃ C	53	25.7	-3.0			
F ₃ C	57	26	-2	3		
CO ₂ H	27	26	-1	3.4	19	-25
CO ₂ HCH ₂	4.0	31	+8	13	26	-1
CO ₂ HCH ₂ CH ₂	7.4	30	+8	34	26	0.5
*CO ₂ HC ₆ H ₄	4.8	29	+5	5	23	-10
*(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	9	30	+6	46	25	-2
*(OH)C ₆ H ₄	5.	38	+29	5	27	-1

^a70°, ionic strength corrected to 0.3 M.

*ortho-Isomer.

Charge effect :

The charge of the leaving group and the overall charge of the complex play a vital role in controlling the rate. The rate decreases with increasing negative charge of the leaving group if the overall charge of the complex is positive, while the reverse is true for a negatively charged complex. This is in keeping with the fact that the transition state is very much like an ion-pair. However, there are a few exceptions to this observation : the aquation of (substituted salicylatopentaamminecobalt(III) (5N = (en)₂NH₃, (trien)NH₃, tetren) being one such¹⁷⁻²². This issue has been resolved by considering the intramolecular acid-base equilibrium between the unbound phenoxide group and the coordinated amine which results in the reactive amido conjugate base. Indeed, the leaving group in the spontaneous aquation of the phenol and phenoxide forms of the salicylato complex is the same salicylato monoanion (HSal⁻).

The charged substrates are susceptible to ion-pairing. A number of studies have been made to understand the role of ion-pairs on the solvolytic reactions of such complexes^{23,24}. The reduction of overall charge of a complex by ion-pairing leads to rate enhancement; this is an electrostatic effect consistent with the I_d mechanism. Ion-pairing generally retards the base catalysed hydrolysis reactions of acidoaminecobalt(III) complexes^{20,24}.

Effects of non-labile ligands :

The classic example is the aquation of $cis\text{-}/trans\text{-}(\text{en})_2\text{CoAX}^{n+}$, where A is a nonlabile ligand and X is the leaving group (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻). With X = Cl⁻, the order of labilising²⁵ effect of A has been established for a number of anionic ligands for both $cis\text{-}$ and $trans\text{-}$ isomers. The OH⁻ and NCS⁻ represent the extrema, the effect for the former being the most significant : $trans\text{-}A : \text{OH}^- > \text{NO}_2^- > \text{N}_3^- > \text{CN}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NCS}^-$; $cis\text{-}A : \text{OH}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_2^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{NCS}^-$.

The $cis\text{-}$ complexes generally react a little faster than their $trans\text{-}$ analogues, except for A = NO₂⁻ and N₃⁻. Strong $trans\text{-}$ labilising action of the S-bonded sulfite ligand (i.e. the ligand $trans$ to the coordinated sulfite is labile) has been documented^{26,27}. In fact, strong kinetic and structural $trans\text{-}$ effect of SO₃²⁻ in $trans\text{-Co}(\text{en})_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{SO}_3)^+$ (i.e. the long Co^{III}-OH₂ bond)²⁶ favours a D-mechanism for the substitution reactions of the aqua ligand by several nucleophiles.

Alkyl groups in *trans*-(alkyl)(DMG)₂Co^{III}X complexes also exert strong labilising effect²⁹, the order (CH₃)₂CH > CH₃CH₂ > CH₃ corresponding to increased sigma (σ) electron donation to Co^{III}. Strong labilising effects arise in corrin and porphyrin complexes relative to the cyclam complexes. This area is yet poorly understood.

Solvent effects :

Water is usually chosen as the medium of reaction. It can not be considered as a simple solvent due to its inherent structuredness which owes its origin to three-dimensional network of hydrogen bonds. In recent years substitution reactions of a wide variety of complexes have been studied in aquo-organic solvent media. It is important to note that both rate and activation parameters are tremendously affected by the medium, despite the fact that the gross mechanism remains intact (i.e. I_d). The correlations of rate constant with Grunwald-Winstein's Y parameter and the bulk dielectric constant of mixed solvents are not satisfactory particularly at high cosolvent content for several mixed solvent systems and complexes of varying structure and steric constraints. Attempts to interpret the solvent effects in terms of hydrophobic interaction, preferential solvation and solvent structure³¹⁻³³ have proved to be rewarding.

Pressure effects :

The volume of activation is a kinetic parameter to distinguish I_d (D) and I_a (A) mechanisms. The expanded transition state for I_d (D) process is likely to be associated with positive values of ΔV[#] and relatively large compressibility as compared to the same for the associative process (I_a or A). However, for the charged complexes the absolute value of ΔV[#] might be offset by the electrostriction effect. Generally speaking, activation volumes coupled with partial molar volumes of the reactants are used to present the volume profile of transition state which further supports I_d mechanism for the cobalt(III) complexes^{34,35}.

Solvent isotope effect :

The N-deuterated halogenoaminocobalt(III) complexes have been used to shed light on the role of solvation on the aquation of such complexes. The N-deuterated complexes aquate in D₂O + H₂O or D₂O media significantly slowly. This has been attributed to the role of hydrogen bonding; D₂O in comparison to H₂O and N-H relative to N-D are poor H-bonding agents. Results favour the solvent assisted dissociative interchange (SAI_d) mechanism^{36,37}.

Entering group effects :

The effect of entering group is hard to be realised in aqueous or mixed aqueous media. Ion-pairing by anionic ligands can be considered here, but then this brings in com-

plications in understanding the intimate mechanism (I_dIP or I_aIP etc.).

The chelating ligands offer the opportunity to examine the ring closure step. The *cis*-(hydroxo)(oxalato)bis-ethylenediaminecobalt(III), *cis*-[(en)₂Co(OH)(O₂CCO₂)], *cis*-(hydroxo)(carbonato)bis-(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III), *cis*-[(en)₂Co(OH)(OCO₂)]³⁸ and *cis*-(hydroxo)(phosphato)bis-(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III), *cis*-[(en)₂Co(OH)(OPO₃)]³⁹, are a few complexes belonging to this set. Notable is the fact that the chelate ring closure rate for the phosphato complex is 500 times faster than that of the carbonato complex, although for both, chelation leads to a four-membered ring. These reactions may involve the intramolecular acid-base equilibrium, H-NCo^{III}-OH ⇌ NCo^{III}-OH₂, followed by ring closure by the vicinal half-bonded ligand with the loss of H₂O (rather than OH⁻) and/or direct attack of the Co^{III}-bound OH at the active site of the half-bonded chelating ligand.

Metal ion catalysed aquation :

The metal ion catalysed aquation of halogeno-, pseudohalogeno- and carboxylato(amine)cobalt(III) has been reported. Hg^{II}, Ag^I and Tl^I are catalysts for halogen/pseudohalogeno complexes. Several other metal ions have been tried for carboxylato(amine)cobalt(III) complexes derived from chelating carboxylate ligands (Tables 3 and 4). Direct evidence for binuclear complexes have been provided in suitable cases. The reactivities of the binuclear species have been correlated with the size, charge and electronic structure of the metal ions^{40,41},

where, X = carboxylate ligand with multiple bonding sites.

Table 3. Values of K_M, ΔH[#] and ΔS[#] for the metal ion induced aquation of (NH₃)₅CoO₂CC₆H₄(o)OM⁴⁺

M ⁿ⁺	10 ⁶ K _M s ⁻¹	ΔH [#] kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS [#] cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Al ³⁺	3.6	36 ± 9	24 ± 27
Ga ³⁺	5.2	31 ± 9	12 ± 27
Fe ³⁺	14	35 ± 9	23 ± 27

*Ref 40

The kinetics of reversible formation of the binuclear complexes in suitable cases (X = C₂O₄²⁻, salicylate, malonate, histidinate, glycinate and picolinate etc.) have been reported recently⁴²⁻⁴⁴. The aquation of *cis*-(diformato)bis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) is catalysed by Cu^{II}⁴⁵. Adduct for-

Table 4. Values of rate constant (k_M) and associated activation parameters for the metal ion induced aquation of $[(NH_3)_5CoO_2CCO_2M]^{(n+1)+}$

Metal ion	$10^6 k_M$ s^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger $kcal\ mol^{-1}$	ΔS^\ddagger $cal\ K^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$
Mn ²⁺	4.6		
Co ²⁺	14.8	30 ± 4	12 ± 12
Ni ²⁺	15.4	30 ± 2	9 ± 7
Cu ²⁺	84	22 ± 1	-9 ± 3
Zn ²⁺	7	28 ± 5	3 ± 15
Al ³⁺	701	27 ± 3	8 ± 11
Ga ³⁺	568	24 ± 1	1 ± 3
In ³⁺	100	25 ± 1	-1 ± 3
Fe ³⁺	1450	28 ± 1	15 ± 3

*Ref. 40.

mation between the reactant and the catalyst (i.e. Cu^{II}) is responsible for the catalysis. The *cis*-diformato complex has a double bridging action, while the *trans*-isomer is not suitable to bind Cu^{II} due to the unfavourable disposition of the formate groups,

$k_2 = (K_M k_M = 3.5 \pm 1 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1} M^{-1})$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 18 \pm 2 kcal\ mol^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -14 \pm 6 cal\ K^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$ at 25°, $I = 0.3 M$.

Base hydrolysis :

The elucidation of mechanism of base hydrolysis of halogeno(amine)cobalt(III) complexes offered the greatest challenge. Such complexes with at least one N-H function undergo fast base hydrolysis (Table 5). Although Garrick proposed the idea of conjugate base formation, direct evidence for the amido conjugate base is still lacking for most Co^{III}-amine complexes. This problem was partly sorted out using halogeno- and carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes in which one of the non-leaving groups is a weakly basic amine, such as aniline⁴⁶, imidazole⁴⁷, benzimidazole⁴⁸, and 2-aminothiazole⁴⁹. Spectroscopic, kinetics and equilibrium measurements for the conjugate base formation were successful for some of these complexes. However, the conjugate base equilibrium preceding the aquation of such complexes in some cases may not be rapidly attained; the evidences accumulated show that the N-H deprotonation may be slow compared to the rate of aquation of the resulting amido bases. Consequently, general base catalysis has been observed in such cases⁵⁰.

Table 5. Rate and activation parameters of base hydrolysis of some *cis*-L₄ACoCl²⁺ complexes

Temp. = 50.0°, $I = 0.3 M$					
L ₄	A	Isomer	$10^{-5} k_{OH}$ $M^{-1} s^{-1}$	ΔH^\ddagger $kcal\ mol^{-1}$	ΔS^\ddagger $cal\ K^{-1}\ mol^{-1}$
trien	NH ₃	β_2	8.0	14.1	12
	NH ₃	α	0.005	21.7	21
	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ NH ₂	α	0.03	21.3	23
	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂	β_2	138	12.2	13
		α	3.3	36.8	65
	C ₆ H ₅ N	β_2	128	12.7	13
imidazole	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ NH ₂	α	0.0038	22.4	23
		β_2	19	21.2	36
bezimidazole		α	0.01	-	-
		β_2	219	15.7	24
(en) ₂	NH ₃		0.00008	-	-
	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ NH ₂		0.00011	23.4	25
	C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂		0.28	31.8	17

The base hydrolysis of carboxylatoaminocobalt(III) complexes offer opportunity to examine the possibilities of C-O and Co-O bond cleavage. The S_N1CB mechanism involving Co-O bond breaking is generally valid. However, for highly activated carboxylatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes with trichloroacetate (Cl₃CCO₂⁻), dichloroacetate (Cl₂CHCO₂⁻), and oxalate (C₂O₄²⁻) as the leaving groups, both C-O and Co-O bond breaking mechanisms seem to operate. The former path involves nucleophilic attack of OH⁻ at the activated C=O group followed by the OH⁻ promoted dissociation (C-O cleavage) of the carboxylate ligand. The observed rate constant is given by eqn. (1),

$$k_{obs} = k_1 [OH^-] + k_2 [OH^-]^2 \quad (1)$$

Oxygen (¹⁸O) exchange experiments⁵¹ elucidated the mechanism. Also oxygen exchange experiments support the C-O cleavage mechanism in the acid-catalysed path of aquation of oxalato- and trichloroacetatopentaamminecobalt(III) complexes.

Addition to Co^{III}-OH :

This includes, as for example, the formation of carbonato⁵², sulfito⁵³, and molybdate⁵¹ complexes. In all these reactions the entering ligand adds on to the N₅Co^{III}-OH moiety through the bound OH. The dissociation of the resulting species also occurs with retention of Co-O bond. The reversible formation of carbonato complexes have been extensively studied⁵⁴. The addition of CO₂ to Co^{III}-OH is fast unlike the aquation of (aqua)(amine)cobalt(III) complexes by carboxylates since the latter reaction involves Co^{III}-OH₂ bond dissociation.

The formation of sulfito complex, $N_5CoOSO_2^+$, is at least 10^6 times faster than the same for the corresponding carbonato complex under comparable conditions. Spectroscopic evidences indicate that in the initial stage oxygen bonded sulfito complex is produced, which undergoes isomerisation to the S-bonded isomer slowly. The S-bonded sulfito complex undergoes changes due to the *trans*-effect. Both the O- and S-bonded sulfito complexes can reduce the Co^{III} centre, the former being relatively more susceptible to internal electron transfer.

Stereochemistry :

Stereochemical changes in the reaction can help to decide the mechanism. Five coordinate intermediate is a model for I_d or D mechanism. Such a species can either be a trigonal bipyramid (TBP) or a square-pyramid (SQPY), may be with some degree of distortion due to non-identical ligands spanning the five coordination sites of central cobalt(III). Stereochemical studies have been made using the *cis*- and *trans*-(en) $_2Co(X)Y^{n+}$ (and several other related complexes).

In the aquation reaction the *trans*-isomer always yields a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-products, while for the *cis*-isomer the aquation product is always the *cis*-isomer²⁵. The steric change is also reflected in the relatively more positive values of the activation entropy for the *trans*-isomers²⁵. The steric change is explained in terms of the structural transformations of the transition state/or transition intermediate. The results indicate that the *trans*-isomer must generate a TBP transition state along the reaction path. It may be noted that a reaction through TBP will yield more *cis*-product starting with the *cis*-reactant than with the *trans*-reactant unless pseudo-reactions can equilibrate the bipyramids. This situation becomes relatively important for long-lived intermediate in the D -mechanism. The loss of optical activity of the optically active isomer cis -(en) $_2CoXY^{n+}$ during the base hydrolysis can be visualised if the amido conjugate base passes on to a TBP intermediate. Racemisation and *cis/trans*-isomerisation are generally observed in the base hydrolysis of the optically active complexes, cis -[Co(en) $_2BX$] $^{2+}$ (B = amine)⁵¹.

In order to examine the nature of the intermediate, product competition experiments have been elegantly designed by Sargeson and coworkers⁵⁰. However, it has been realised that the intermediates are highly reactive and presumably the life-times of such species are a few pico seconds. In that time-scale solvent barrier plays a dominant role in controlling the dynamics of such species.

Redox reactions :

Cobalt(III) complexes have been used as models for electron transfer reactions^{12, 55}. The electron transfer through

Cl bridge in $(NH_3)_5Co^{III}Cl-Cr^{II}(OH_2)_5$ has been demonstrated through product analysis. Varying structure, basicity, donor function and dentate nature of the bridging ligand for several reducing metal ions like Cr^{II} , Fe^{II} , Eu^{II} , V^{II} and Cu^I have provided great insight into the mechanism of electron transfer reactions, actively pursued by Taube and his school.

The oxidation of molecules/ions coordinated to cobalt(III) centre has been investigated. The cobalt(III) centre is reduced when the ligand is oxidised by external oxidising agents. The coordinated ligands react much slower than the free ligand, which is a consequence of diminished availability of electron in the ligand skeleton due to coordination⁵⁶

Photochemistry :

The photochemical reactions of cobalt(III) complexes offer another challenging field. The ligand field bands ($^1A_{1g} \leftrightarrow ^1T_{1g}$; $^1A_{1g} \leftrightarrow ^1T_{2g}$) and the ligand-to-metal charge transfer bands are used for excitation. The irradiation in the ligand field band region leads to photochemical aquation with low quantum yield; photo-reduction (of Co^{III}) and photo-aquation of the complexes occur when the charge transfer band (CTTM) is excited. A variety of products are expected and hence identification of products poses a challenging problem in this area.

The photo-isomerisation of complex ions offers another interesting area. Transients are generated by flash photolysis and their reactivities can be studied. One such case is the photochemical isomerisation of (tetren)Co-SO $_3^+$ to (tetren)Co-OSO $_2^+$ by flashing light on the S-bonded isomer⁵⁸. The oxidation of ethylenediaminetetraacetate by irradiation of $Co(en)_3^{3+}$ in the presence of EDTA shows that Werner type complexes can be used as photo-sensitisers.

Conclusion :

The kinetic aspects of cobalt(III) complexes are briefly presented here. This area still provides tremendous opportunity to continue investigative research. The scope has been widened since a wide variety of such complexes can be synthesised which can be used as models for kinetics and thermodynamic investigations.

References

- 1 J M Pratt, *Pure Appl Chem*, 1993, 7, 1513
- 2 I N Bronsted and R Livingstone, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1927, 49, 435
- 3 F J Garrick, *Nature (London)*, 1937, 139, 507
- 4 G Basolo and R G Pearson, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions", Wiley, New York, 1958
- 5 H Taube, *Chem Rev*, 1952, 50, 69

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- 6 C. K. Jorgenson, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1955, 9, 605.
- 7 D. D. Brown, C. K. Ingold and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2673; 1956, 2680; 1956, 2696; C. K. Ingold, R. S. Nyholm and M. L. Tobe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1691; 1956, 1707.
- 8 A. McAuley, M. N. Malik and J. Hill, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 2461.
- 9 C. H. Langford and H. B. Gray, "Ligand Substitution Processes", Benjamin, New York, 1965
- 10 A. Haim, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 426.
- 11 Z. Fujita, C. S. Varley and J. Zasko, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 3013.
- 12 F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1967.
- 13 S. C. Chan and K. Y. Hui, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 2529.
- 14 D. A. Buckingham, B. M. Foxman and A. M. Sargeson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 1790.
- 15 S. C. Chan and C. L. Lee, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2649.
- 16 S. C. Chan and O. W. Lau, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 1851.
- 17 A. C. Dash and B. Mohanty, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 1179.
- 18 A. C. Dash and B. Mohanty, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 309.
- 19 A. C. Dash and B. Mohanty, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 183.
- 20 A. C. Dash and M. S. Dash, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 2873.
- 21 A. C. Dash and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 4011.
- 22 A. C. Dash and R. C. Nayak, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, 25, 2237.
- 23 S. H. Laurie and C. B. Monk, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 724; M. B. M. Campbell, M. R. Wendt and C. B. Monk, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1972, 1714.
- 24 A. C. Dash and R. K. Nanda, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 298.
- 25 C. H. Langford and V. S. Sastri in "MTP International Review of Science, Reaction Mechanisms in Inorganic Chemistry", ed. M. L. Tobe, Butterworth, London, 1972. Vol. 9, p. 213.
- 26 D. R. Stranks and J. K. Yandell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 751; J. K. Yandell and L. A. Tomlins, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, 31, 561.
- 27 A. C. Dash and B. Padhy, *Indian J. Chem. Sect. A*, 1989, 28, 1054.
- 28 C. L. Ratson, A. H. White and J. K. Yandell, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, 31, 993.
- 29 A. L. Crumbliss and W. K. Wilmarth, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 2593.
- 30 W. C. Randall and W. A. Alberty, *Biochemistry*, 1967, 6, 1520; E. B. Fleischer, S. Jacobs and I. Mestichelli, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 2527.
- 31 A. C. Dash, J. Pradhan and A. N. Acharya, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1996, 3353; A. C. Dash, A. N. Acharya and S. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1999, 31, 55; A. C. Dash and A. Acharya, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1994, 3293; A. C. Dash and S. Dash, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, 36, 849; A. C. Dash and P. K. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1990, 22, 307; A. C. Dash, N. M. Dash, P. K. Das and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, 3753; A. C. Dash and S. Das, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1997, 136; (M) 1997, 925; A. C. Dash and S. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1999, 38
32. K. H. M. Halwani and C. F. Wells, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1990, 1741.
33. O. Grancicova and V. Holba, *Transition Met. Chem. (Wienheim)*, 1994, 9, 322.
34. "Inorganic High Pressure Chemistry, Kinetics and Mechanisms", ed. R. van Eldik, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1986; R. van Eldik, T. Asano and W. J. le Noble, *Chem. Rev.*, 1989, 88, 549
35. G. Stochel and R. van Eldik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, 29, 2075.
36. A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1989, 2797.
37. S. C. Chan and F. Leh, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2010.
38. D. J. Francis and R. B. Jordan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 6626.
39. S. F. Lincoln and D. R. Stranks, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 57
40. A. C. Dash and R. K. Nanda, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 2024, 1974, 13, 655.
41. A. C. Dash and R. K. Nanda, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 1595; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 289.
42. A. C. Dash and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 2336; A. C. Dash, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 837; A. C. Dash and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 1265; A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1992, 24, 155.
43. A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and A. Acharya, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1993, 1023.
44. A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and R. Das, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, 30, 1001; N. N. Das and A. C. Dash, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, 31, 678; 1993, 32, 531.
45. A. C. Dash, R. K. Nanda and N. N. Das, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, 12, 338.
46. R. N. Nanda and R. K. Nanda, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 104; S. C. Chan and O. W. Lau, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 1851.
47. A. C. Dash and S. K. Mohapatra, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 246; A. C. Dash and B. Mohanty, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 183.
48. A. C. Dash and S. K. Mohapatra, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1207; A. C. Dash and S. K. Mohapatra, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1978, 40, 1596; A. C. Dash, M. S. Dash and S. K. Mohapatra, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1979, 354; (M), 1979, 4531; A. C. Dash, B. Mohanty and S. K. Mohapatra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 312.
49. A. C. Dash and J. Pradhan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, 30, 601.
50. M. L. Tobe in "Advances in Inorganic and Bioinorganic Mechanisms", ed. A. G. Sykes, Academic, New York, 1983, Vol. 2.
51. D. A. House, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, 23, 223.
52. R. van Eldik and D. A. Palmer, *Chem. Rev.*, 1983, 83, 651.
53. R. van Eldik and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 880. A. C. Dash, A. A. El-Awady and G. M. Harris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981,

- 20, 3160, A C Dash and A N Acharya, *Proc Indian Acad Sci (Chem Sci)*, 1993, **105**, 225, A C Dash and B Padhy, *Indian J Chem Sect A*, 1989, **28**, 1054, A C Dash and K C Jena, *Transition Met Chem*, 1997, **22**, 141, A C Dash, K C Jena, A Roy, D Mukherji and S Aditya, *J Chem Soc, Dalton Trans*, 1997, 2451, A C Dash, A N Acharya and A K Patnaik, *Transition Met Chem*, 1998, **23**, 45
- 54 M C Ghosh, P Bhattacharya and P Banerjee, *Coord Chem Rev*, 1988, **91** 1
- 55 R G Linck in "MTP International Review Science, Reaction Mechanism in Inorganic Chemistry", ed M L Tobe, Butterworths, London, 1972, Vol 9, p 303
- 56 P Saffir and H Faube, *J Am Chem Soc*, 1960 **82** 13, J P Candlin and H Halpern, *J Am Chem Soc* 1963 **85** 1518 R M Milburn and H C Kruszyna, *Inorg Chem*, 1971, **10** 1578, E S Gould and V S Srinivasan, *Inorg Chem* 1981, **20** 208 R K Nanda and N K Mohanty, *Indian, J Chem, Sect A* 1982, **21**, 522, A C Dash, R K Nanda and P Mohanty *Indian J Chem, Sect A* 1984, **23**, 162, A C Dash, P Mohanty and R K Nanda, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1984, **61**, 940
- 57 R B Bucat and D W Watts in Ref 55, p 159
- 58 A C Dash, N Dash, S Aditya and A Roy *Indian J Chem, Sect A*. 1988, **27**, 398